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Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement: A Mixed Method

Lysa D. Loayon,* Kristy Jane R. Meugna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study aimed to describe the lived experiences of Filipino major students in a local college on the between corrective feedback and student engagement and their learning. This study engaged a mixed-methods design, utilizing a parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were Filipino major students from all grade levels. One hundred ninety students were randomly selected for the quantitative and 10 for the qualitative: five (5) in-depth interviews and five (5) focus group discussions, which were purposefully selected. In the quantitative phase, the results revealed a specific correlation analysis between perceived corrective feedback and student engagement among Filipino majors is high. Additionally, the students' insights shared fostered a helpful environment for student engagement, and teaching-learning strategies. Moreover, the result of qualitative phase from different participants have diverse perspective especially on their insights and experiences. Lastly, the qualitative data mostly corroborated the qualitative data.

Keywords: *corrective feedback, teacher and student engagement, Filipino major students, Philippines*

Introduction

In a dynamic educational environment, teachers play a critical role in promoting student engagement through the strategic use of corrective feedback. Corrective feedback, based on educational principles and educational psychology, serves as a compass to guide students toward deeper understanding and skill acquisition. Through targeted instruction, constructive criticism, and supportive encouragement, teachers not only identify areas for improvement, but also develop proactive strategies that foster student engagement, resilience, and a growth mindset which create a learning environment. Hence, this feedback loop is a valuable catalyst for increasing student engagement, fostering intrinsic motivation, and ultimately fostering continued academic and personal growth (Nassaji, 2021).

In international settings particularly in the USA, it has been revealed that student engagement is considered to be one of the hardest challenges faced by almost all teachers. This is due to the fact that students come from a variety of backgrounds and are diverse learners. Poor student accomplishment results from students' difficulty participating in any activities that teachers assign. They report less engagement and participation. Teachers have stated that low student engagement is partly caused by their districts' unclear standards and accountability. Many students find the planned activities boring and uninteresting. Additionally, teachers claim that their incapacity to work one-on-one with pupils remotely is another factor contributing to the difficulty of fully engaging students. Additionally, teachers claimed that their incapacity to work one-on-one with pupils remotely is another factor contributing to the difficulty of fully engaging students. Students' motivation to do online tasks may be impacted by this lack of timely communication with their lecturers, which also suggests another source of unfairness for those students who are less capable of controlling their own learning.

According to a developmental perspective, academic failure and dropping out are the outcomes of a long-term process of disengagement from school, since disengaged students are more likely to struggle academically, drop out, and exhibit problem behaviors. Therefore, improving student involvement could aid in averting these subpar student results (Chatti, 2021).

In the national setting, it has also been found that student engagement is a challenge many teachers face. Teachers identified a variety of factors, from the long-term effects of disruptive behavior to a lack of intrinsic motivation in key topics, as reasons why students find it difficult to remain involved in class. Because of this, the idea of student engagement seems to appeal to teachers who observe that a large number of students lack enthusiasm and involvement. In many ways, accommodating individual differences can be extremely difficult. They also emphasized how different students are and how difficult it is for them to take in and digest information. These problems have led to significant absenteeism and dropout rates, which have a detrimental effect on both the students' and the school's overall performance (Urias, 2022).

The study's urgency stems from the growing significance of providing students with constructive criticism and the impact it has on their engagement. It is essential that BSED Filipino students comprehend, respect, and effectively interact with teachers when handling corrective criticism in an increasingly interconnected environment where student engagement is growing more diversified. It is crucial for learning and growth, carrying both. It clears up misunderstandings, hones abilities, and promotes progress. Additionally, timely and constructive correction improves communication, develops competence, and fosters a collaborative learning environment, making this study socially relevant. By gaining insight into BSED-Filipino students in KCAST and acquiring corrective feedback, we can improve and develop techniques to better equip future Filipino educators in connecting effectively and assisting students from different levels of their engagement. Furthermore, the knowledge gained from this study can aid in closing the gap between students' learning outcomes and the teacher's corrective comments. engagement that promotes a more inclusive and peaceful atmosphere.

Various studies have been carried out that is somewhat related to the study that will be undertaken by the researchers such as the study

of Lira-Gonzales et al (2021) entitled, “Students Engagement with Teacher Written Corrective Feedback in a French as a Foreign Language Classroom”. This study is useful as it provides new understanding of the precise relationship between corrective feedback from teachers and student engagement. Another study conducted Language Classroom”. Learner Beliefs and Learner Engagement with Written Corrective Feedback by Han (2017). Lastly, Student Engagement with Automated Written Corrective Feedback study by Koltovskaia (2020), this study examines student engagement with automated written corrective feedback (AWCF). Yet, each of the aforementioned studies is unique in that it offers a fresh perspective on the precise connection between teacher-provided corrective feedback and student involvement. This study aims to investigate the ways in which tailored feedback techniques can encourage student involvement. This is crucial for fostering critical thinking and self-confidence in addition to academic performance. However, using a mixed method research approach, this study examines the relationship between corrective feedback and student engagement in Filipino education students at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. It focuses not only on the learners' cognitive engagement but also on their emotional and behavioral engagement.

The dissemination plan is to disseminate the results of a comprehension research study that examines the connection between student participation and corrective feedback among Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology Filipino majors. Furthermore, this study's research findings will offer a thorough understanding and the potential to develop a strong plan of action that will benefit everyone, particularly teachers, students, and larger audiences. The study investigates the potential benefits of a teacher's deliberate use of corrective feedback for raising student engagement and academic achievement. All students will benefit from a more welcoming and stimulating learning environment if corrective feedback techniques are adopted.

Research Questions

This study investigates the exploration of corrective feedback of teachers and students' engagement among all BSED Filipino education students, using mix- method research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both qualitative and quantitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to address the research matter at hand. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of corrective feedback from teachers towards student engagement among Filipino students?
2. What are the lived experiences of BSED-Filipino about the corrective feedback of teachers and their engagement in the classroom setting?
3. What insight can the students share to their fellow students and to the academe in general?
4. To what extent does the quantitative data results corroborate with the qualitative data results?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researcher employed mixed method strategy combining elements of quantitative research and qualitative research in order to give a more explanation of the research subject and to answer your research question. Mixed method can help you gain a more completed picture than a standalone quantitative or qualitative study as it integrates benefits of both methods (George, 2021).

Combining the two types of data means you benefit from both the detailed, contextualized of qualitative data the generalized externally valid insights of quantitative data. To study complex topics, a mixed method approached can be used to integrate and combine several data sources. It was also stated in the preceding section, that it enables researchers to seek a wide picture of their study by allowing them to see a phenomenon via multiple viewpoints and research lenses (Shorten & Smith, 2017).

In context of this study, the application of mixed method approached is particularly advantageous. This approached allows for the integration of both qualitative and quantitative data sources, enabling more comprehensive examination of corrective feedback of teachers among students' engagement in all BSED Filipino students. It aimed to capitalized on the strengths of each approached, providing a more comprehensive understanding of a research problem.

The convergent parallel design is a mixed-method research approach that involved collecting both quantitative and qualitative data independently, with the intent to cover or merged the results for a comprehensive understanding of the research question, quantitative and qualitative data are collected simultaneously, analyzed separately, and then integrated during the interpretation phase to provide a more robust and holistic perspective. This design is particularly useful when researchers seek to triangulate findings or gain a deeper understanding of a phenomenon by examining multiple angles. This method preserved the research's objectivity throughout data collection and processing before combining or merging the findings throughout the overall interpretation (Creswell & Plano, 2018).

In context of my study the used of convergent parallel design is crucial. This design is rooted in the broader framework of mixed method research, which emphasized the strength of both qualitative and quantitative methods. This research approach allowed for simultaneous use of both quantitative and qualitative method to examined the corrective feedback of teachers and students' engagements among BSED Filipino education students. By giving equal weight to both quantitative and qualitative data, this design ensured a comprehensive and objective exploration of the subject matter, preserved the integrity of the research process from data collection to final interpretation.

Participants

The main participants of the study both quantitative and qualitative strands are described in this section. The participants are essential in conducting this study as they are the primary sources of data needed in this study. With them, the goal of the study will be achieved and realized.

Quantitative Phase

The respondent of this study involved the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino students of Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology during the Second Semester of Academic Year 2023-2024 totaling of one hundred ninety (190) respondents. They were chosen as the respondents because the study focused on corrective feedback of teachers and students' engagement. Since this study purpose involved students' satisfaction, it was fitting and valid to include students from all Filipino major students in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology (KCAST). Furthermore, to establish randomness and maintain the element of science in the study, satisfied random sampling was used.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sampling</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	191	101	28.00 %
Second Year	75	40	11.00%
Third Year	60	32	8.80%
Fourth Year	34	18	4.98%
Total	360	190	52.78%

Further, one possible method was determined through stratified random sampling. This approach involves dividing the population into sub groups or strata based on relevant characteristics, such as age, gender, or academic performance, and then selecting a random sample from each stratum. Stratified random sampling helped ensure that the sample was representative of the population and that each subgroup was adequately represented in the sample, which can increase the generalizability of the findings. However, this method required that the population was well-defined and that the relevant characteristics for stratification were known (Etikan & Bala, 2017).

The stratified random sampling was particularly appropriate in this study because the respondent of this research were randomly selected based on strata, which in this case, were the students from all programs in Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology (KCAST). To compute the sample, the researcher first gathered the data on the population of respondents through writing a formal request letter to the college registrar, requesting access to the population of respondents. After obtaining the data, the researcher will send the information to a statistician for computation of study sample.

Random sampling, stratified random sampling ensured that each stratum was represented in the sample and could provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen, 2020). In conclusion, this sampling method was particularly appropriate for this study because the respondents, which are the Filipino education students were selected, which in this case are all year level of the Filipino education program in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensured that all of the respondent in the population had equal chances of being selected.

Furthermore, stratified random selection is employed to choose samples from a particular population of the study. A stratified random sampling method was a way of selecting a sample in which the researcher divided a group of people into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared features of the members and then chosen randomly from each stratum to generate the final sample (Simkus, 2023). In this study, the shared characteristics of the samples included their education level, degree, or program.

Lastly, in selecting and choosing the qualified respondents for the study, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as the basis and guide for the selection process. This included: (1) must be enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in a Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Filipino; (3) must be currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2023-2024) (4) must be male or female or any gender, and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Table 1.2. *Profiles of the Participants*

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Female	1st year
IDI-02	Female	2nd year
IDI-03	Female	2nd year
IDI-04	Male	3rd year
IDI-05	Female	3rd year
FGD-01	Female	4th year
FGD-02	Female	3rd year
FGD-03	Female	3rd year
FGD-04	Male	2nd year
FGD-05	Female	1st year

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, just like the quantitative phase, the participants were Filipino major students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The selection of the participants is justified because the intended participants of the study were Filipino major students. Thus, they are the only ones capable of providing authentic accounts about the research topic. There was total of 10 participants from the Filipino teacher education student program, 5 were chosen for in-depth interviews and the remaining 5 participated in focus groups. All of these individuals must be enrolled KCAST students in the first, second, third, fourth year of the course. It is important to note that participants in the data collection, for the quantitative stages were not permitted to engage in the qualitative phase.

This conformed to the suggestion and recommendations of Creswell and Creswell (2018) which pointed out that a researcher may have between 10 to 50 participants as being sufficient in qualitative research depending on the type of research and research questions. Consequently, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique in selecting and choosing the participants to be included and involved both for the IDI and FGD. As explained, purposive sampling was a sampling strategy in which participants were chosen because they possessed traits that required in the samples for the study. In other words, with purposive sampling, participants were chosen on purpose (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Lastly, for the selection process, the researcher set an inclusion criterion as a basis. This included: (1) must be enrolled in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology; (2) must be enrolled in a Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English; (3) must be currently enrolled in the previous academic year 2023-2024) must (4) can be male or female or any gender; and (5) must have the willingness to participate in the study.

Instrument

In this section, the research tools for gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed.

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized an adopted survey questionnaire to assess students attitude used a Corrective Feedback and Students Engagement survey questionnaire which was adapted from Amari, S. (2022). The said questionnaire used a five-point Likert Scale which included the following indicators: Motivating method of Corrective Feedback, Corrective Feedback Content, Methods of Utilizing Corrective Feedback and Behavioral Engagement, Emotional Engagement, and Cognitive Engagement conduct were the indicators used in the aforementioned questionnaire, which employed a five-point Likert Scale.

In the quantitative phase, the instrument used was as a constructed questionnaire. The survey questionnaire had acceptable values ranging from 1 (represents the lowest rating) and 5 (represents the highest rating), for each answer they felt best represented the question. First, the questionnaire focused on corrective feedback and the second one focused on student engagement. Moreover, Likert Scale was suitable for measuring constructs, attitudes and stimuli that are not readily perceivable in human senses. Despite the questionnaire being adapted, it was still subjected to expert validation.

Lastly, this questionnaire provided a variety of instruments, justifications and interpretations. To easy evaluate the data gathered in the study, the researcher made a table that represented the five orderable categories of Corrective Feedback of teacher and Student's Engagement with their respective means and that is as follows:

Student Engagement. The questionnaire for this variable was adopted from the study of Palmero, G. (2019), which had three indicators, namely: cognitive engagement, emotional engagement, and behavioral engagement. The tool is 15 the items are evenly distributed across the three specified indicators, ensuring a thorough evaluation of participants' responses. This distribution is essential for accurately capturing insights related to the variable in question.

Qualitative Phase

In the qualitative phase, an interview guide was used that contained the grand core questions and along with probing and supporting questions which were used both in the in-depth interview and focus group discussions. External validators will also reviewed the design of the questions to determined if it measured what they sought to test or they obtained the data required for the study. Furthermore, in this strand, the researcher used this validated interview guide to validate the finding from the quantitative phase. Finally, the interview guide was divided into two sections. The first was for the letter of authorization for the participants, and the second was for the actual interview.

Validity of the Instruments

The instruments used in the study underwent a validation process before they were administered and distributed to the respondents of the study. In the current study, the survey questionnaires were adopted from published research that dealt with Corrective Feedback (CF) and Student Engagement (SE). As a result, these studies were validated, and the Cronbach alpha of the pilot testing was provided. In the project, however, the adopted questionnaires were subjected to pilot testing to ensure their dependability. The tool was then evaluated by the panelist before pilot testing to ensure that its content was corrected and that it measured the designed appropriately. These validators all held doctorates and masters in their fields of study. The researcher will took this into account to ensure that the

validators were reliable and competent enough to validate the tool to be utilized in the study.

In addition, an interview guide used in the study to see if the qualitative data corroborated with the quantitative results. Similarly, an informed consent form employed, the contents of which described the goal of the study. The participants were able to read the consent to be come aware and knowledgeable about their involvement in the study. Similarly, participants were properly informed that their participation were voluntary and personal, and their identification and personal information would be treated with the utmost confidentiality. Finally, the entire interview process took place in areas that were distraction-free and convenient for the participants.

Procedure

From the time the researcher is done with the routing of the manuscript to its panelists, the research manuscript was submitted to the Research Ethics of Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences to check whether the study adhered the mandated protocol needed for the ethical consideration and trustworthiness of the study. Additionally, the researcher requested an Ethics Clearance to conduct the study. Then, after conforming to the recommendations as per protocol evaluation given by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the institution, the following stages to be done by the researcher in gathered the data needed for the study.

First, the researcher wrote a letter asking permission to conduct the study. A request letter will be signed by the adviser attached with an endorsement letter signed by the College President of the Kapalong College of Agriculture, Science, and Technology. Afterward, the approval of the college president of the institution meant that the researcher could begin gathered the data by distributing the survey questionnaire to the research respondents. Meanwhile, before collecting data from respondents, the researcher requested a gatekeeper in KCAST to assist her in carrying out the study. An orientation was conducted by the researcher to make the gatekeepers fully aware of the nature and purpose of the study. Also, part of the orientation is that the researcher provided the gatekeepers with informed consent form. Then, gatekeepers assisted the researcher in the conduct of the study by giving the informed consent form to the respondents in their designated school along with the researcher. After that, the researcher discussed and oriented the respondents about the goal and purpose of the study which is stipulated in the informed consent form. Also, as to what their role in the conduct study. After the orientation, the respondents signed the form which indicated that they fully understand the purpose and goal of the study. Thus, they voluntarily agreed to participate as the research respondents. After these essential preliminaries in conducting the study, was the different essential and significant measures for gathering data in both qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were discussed below. In this process, the optimum confidentiality of data is assured.

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, the researcher conducted the study on a face-to-face basis. This means the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaire the participants. To be specific about the data gathering process, below were taken by the researcher.

First, after the respondents signed the informed consent form, they were given the survey questionnaire which contained different questions for the two variables which are the Corrective Feedback and Student Engagement. In the questionnaire, the respondents were not required to include their names as this was optional. Also, they were given ample time to complete answering the questions to ensure that valid and reliable answers were obtained.

Second, after the respondents had completely answered all the stipulated questions in the survey questionnaire, the researcher and the gatekeeper completely retrieved the questionnaire in preparation for the tallying process. Consequently, the respondents were given tokens of appreciation as a form of gratitude for their voluntary participation in the study. Additionally, in the tallying of the responses, the researcher requested a format to the statistician for easy treatment of the data afterward;

Third, after the tallying of the research data, the analysis and treatment of the data followed. The tallied data were given to the research statistician who was capable and knowledgeable in data analysis and data treatment;

Fourth, when the statistician will return the result of the data analysis and treatment, the researcher will analyze and interpret the results. Of course, this is with the help and guidance of the research adviser. This was to ensure that the analysis done is truthful and correct.

Lastly, in the whole process of data gathering, data treatment, and data analysis and interpretation, it was guaranteed that the data collected from the research respondents would remain confidential. All of the answered survey questionnaires were placed on a locked box with a unique and strong pin code so that, it is only the researcher could gained access to it. With these measured it guaranteed that no other person could access the gathered data.

Qualitative Strand

When the results and findings of the quantitative phase were already available, the data gathering under the qualitative phase began. The main purpose of this phase was to confirm and affirm results in the first phase through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. In this phase, the researcher followed the procedures:

First, since the respondents already signed the informed consent before the conduct of the quantitative phase, the researcher chose 10 participants from the same sample to be part of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion. In the selection process, the researcher sought the assistance of the gatekeeper. Then, the gatekeeper was then guided on which participants were qualified to be

included in the interview based on the inclusion criteria of the researcher.

Second, when the 10 participants were already chosen, another orientation was conducted. This orientation informed and educated the participants about the next stage of the research. They were fully informed about their role in this stage of the research. In addition, in case any of the identified participants withdrew from the study during orientation the researcher respected their decision. Hence, the gatekeeper and researcher sought for new participants and volunteers.

Third, after the orientation, a separate one-on-one interview with the first 5 informants began. This was conducted via Google Meet, over the phone, messenger, or any platform that the informants preferred. After the in-depth interview with the 5 informants, the focus group discussion with the remaining 5 participants started. Online platform agreed upon and convenient for the participants was utilized in the whole discussion.

Fourth, after the interview process, the researcher transcribed all of the individual responses of the 5 informants in verbatim form. A separated transcript was prepared for the 5 participants in the focus group discussion.

Fifth, once the individual transcript of all the 5 informants were available as well as the transcript for the focus group discussion, the researcher gave each informants and participants a copy of their transcript. This allowed them to check and verify whether the transcript is right or wrong. In addition, if any of the participants wished to delete part of the transcript, or if they wish to add more responses, the researcher compiled with their requests. Lastly, when the verified copy of the individual transcripts from the 5 informants and one from the focus group discussion were ready, the analysis of data which is the thematic analysis will followed.

Data Analysis

This section discusses the detailed description of the different processes that were employed in analyzing the gathered data from both the quantitative and qualitative phases of the study.

Quantitative Phase

The mean and other descriptive statistics used in the quantitative data analysis to evaluate the respondents average responses. Additionally, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and the T-test is employed to identify the significant variations in the participants corrective feedback when categorized according to their profile. In depth-interview analysis was conducted using the survey data that were gathered. After the survey were retrieved, the total data was being handled appropriately.

Qualitative Strand

In the qualitative phase, the data collected during the conduct of the interviews were analyzed to come up with conclusions that affirmed and supported the findings from the quantitative phase. As explained, the analysis of data in research involved summarizing the mass of data collected and presenting the results in a way that communicates the most important features of the study (Harding, 2013).

In the study, data analysis was done after the process of transcribing the results of the in-depth interview and focus group discussion among the participants. The researcher used coding and thematic analysis in analyzing the collected and gathered data. Further, in displaying and presenting the data, it organized into different categories based on similar responses from the different participants. The process is called thematic analysis.

As defined, thematic analysis is the method utilized in analyzing and reporting the pattern of themes in the study. Braun & Clarke (2013) stated that thematic analysis is a flexible data analysis plan that qualitative researcher use to generated themes from interview data. To familiarize the data, I would listened to and transcribed the recorded interviews of the participants and read through them repeatedly to identify similar answer given by the participants. After familiarizing the data, coding of the data began, I will used the coding of the data to arrive at and generate themes, ideas, and categories. Then similar passages of text were marked with a code label so that they could easily be retrieved at a later stage for further comparison and analysis.

After the codes were clustered together, I will labeled the clusters based on the meaning or relationships shared among the codes. Naming the codes was the next process involved the utilization of the labels created for the theme and providing a comprehensive name that described the relationship or meaning conveyed in that specific theme.

Lastly, to strengthen the reliability of the data, I would also consult my data analyst who is an expert in the field, and my research adviser for further verification of the data. Then, I will present the findings and interpretation of the data through tabular forms for better understanding and elaboration.

Ethical Considerations

In order to keep trust of the KCAST English teacher education students, the study's top prioritices safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality. We are taking steps to ensure that these ethical issues are thoughtfully addressed in order to maintained the participants' trust throughout the study.

The researcher is meticulously abiding by ethical principles including respect for others, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality in order to ensure that ethical requirements are met. The participants' rights and well-being

are given high importance by these guidelines, which directing the study's conduct in a responsible and polite manner (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is a code of conduct that emphasized the need of treating research participants with respect and decency and respecting their freedom to independently select whether or not participate in a study. Participants were fully aware of the study's goals, methods, risks, and advantages in order to follow this advice. Obtaining informed consent which is defined as willingly engaging into an agreement based on informed understanding it is necessary to uphold this principle. The researcher can make sure that the study is carried out morally and in a way that respects the rights and autonomy of the participants by respecting the concept of the respect for individuals (Munhall, 2012; Scott, 2013).

The researcher first obtained the participants' consent before starting the interviews to avoid schedule issues with classes or other obligations. This ensured that the researcher's presence did not interfere with the participants' schedules and to avoid having to reschedule or canceling the interviews.

As I will conduct my research, I established a respectful and courteous rapport with the participants and requesting their consent before recording any interactions. I will also allow the participants to ask me questions whenever they want while maintaining the confidentiality of the focus group discussions and in-depth interviews. Participants may also refuse not to respond to challenging questions. By getting to know the participants and treating them well, I am able to conduct the study in an honest and polite manner.

Consent is fundamental to research ethics and a way to show respect for study subjects. By obtaining their informed consent, participants will be fully informed of the aims and purposes of the research they are being asked to participate in. In-depth interviews and focus discussions will be conducted with the participants consent, which was obtained in writing. They will inform of the study's findings and recommendations in order to maintain transparency and keep them inform (Creswell,2012).

In addition, I give letters to each participant, an authorization and consent outlining the specifics of the study, all important information like techniques, design, and procedures, in order to assure the ethical conduct of the study. The participants' right to know the study's finding is also disclosed by the researcher to them. The researcher can make sure that the study will carry out in a responsible and respectful manner by adhering to these ethical principles. Furthermore, the research will informed the participants that they have the right to ask questions during the interview, rights to refuse to answer sensitive questions, and rights to leave the interview without any explanation. If the participants leave in the middle of the interview, the researcher respected the participants decision to not finish the interview. Lastly, the researcher would make sure that all participants have the rights to be informed of the study results with enthusiastic and driven to contribute to the success of this study.

Beneficence. required commitment of the participants rather maximizing profits that are due to them. Anonymity of the interviewee was kept in order not to put each participant into risks. At all times, participants were protected, so all files of information were not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

In my study, I kept the data secured to protect the participants and ensured that the outcome of the research would be beneficial to the research participants. Similarly, the participants were given access to the results of my study for this might help them. Furthermore, in order to protect the beneficent principle, I am taking steps to maintained the anonymity and secrecy of the participants remarks and personal information. To minimized any potential risks, I will be communicating with the participants via social media rather than in-person meetings. By taking these actions, I am able to protect the participants interest and demonstrate commitment to ethical research practices.

Confidentiality. towards the data, various approaches used to arrive at results and conclusions, including the protection of individuals including the protection of individuals indicating that no identifiable information about the participants shared. All materials, including audio recordings, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data, and other items, should be thrown away after the data has been analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect participant identities and ensured compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I am using discreted coding to identify each participant's response. This method calls for carefully framing any information that could be used to identify individuals by name, gender, race, or employment/location. By using suitable code and other protections, I can concealed the participant's identities and ensured that their privacy is being protected. Research data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the accomplishment of the study.

Furthermore, there was a possible risk of harm in terms of social liabilities when the data is carefully disclosed to others. As such data of the study be maintained private and secured to avoid this incident from happening. The researcher made sure to emphasized to the respondents that their safety, identity, and personal information would be protected and their participation in the study would be important to them. To create an error-free collection, the researcher removes identities from the data. A clean data collection does not contained any data that could be used to identify the respondents, such as names or addresses (such identifying data could be stored in separate, secure files elsewhere). The data shall be stored and destroyed three years after the study is accomplished.

Justice. required a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as the results of the study. Therefore, acknowledging the contribution of all the respondents should be highlighted as they become an integral part of the success of this study. It was

recommended that respondents should be given due credits in all of their participation extended in our research. Also, they were given to them as assign of gratitude for their efforts in the study. The researcher is hoping that through this study, they will be set free into whatever negative experience they had as informants and maintain a good bearing on what positive contributions they could offer in this study (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

In this study, researcher ensured that all ethical standards were addressed to protect the rights of the participants. Also, ensured that all the research questions that were asked to the participants were of relevance to my study and not with any personal intention and interest. Any topics and speculations which are not part of my research objective will not be discussed and entertained.

Results and Discussion

This section, the outcomes of the data are presented, breaking them down the in both quantitative and qualitative phases. The first phase deals with the quantitative part which displays the level of Filipino major students in terms of corrective feedback that significantly predicts their learning engagement. The second phase deals with the qualitative part which was presented in a matrix form. This matrix shows the responses of the participants on their lived experiences regarding to corrective feedback of teacher and student engagement. Also, the matrix contains the issues probed, core ideas, or categories, essential themes and supporting theoretical perspectives. Further, another matrix shows the data integration of the salient quantitative and qualitative findings.

Level of Corrective Feedback and Student Engagement

The results of the survey conducted are presented here. The overall mean, the items with the highest and lowest ratings per indicators were given. Corrective Feedback as the independent variable of the study has three indicators namely: motivating method, corrective feedback content and methods of utilizing corrective feedback. Shown in Table 2 was the level of Corrective Feedback.

Motivating method. The overall mean of the level of corrective feedback In terms of motivating method, the mean score is 3.81 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No.1 Observing that the teacher explains how to check mistakes got the highest mean score of 4.02 which is described as high. This means that is oftentimes manifested. On the other hand, Item No. 5 Thinking the teacher use the same method of correction with all skills was the lowest item rated by the participants with a mean score of 3.62. This rating is described as high. This means that is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 2. *Status of Corrective feedback*

Variables and Indicators	Mean	Description
A. Motivating Method		
1. Observing that the teacher explains how to check mistakes.	4.02	High
2. Noticing that the teacher supports me with resources so I can improve my abilities.	3.88	High
3. Believing that the teacher will point out all my mistakes.	3.83	High
4. Observing that the teacher includes the page number of the textbooks so I can review my knowledge.	3.72	High
5. Thinking the teacher use the same method of correction with all skills.	3.62	High
Category Mean	3.81	High
B. Corrective Feedback content		
1. Observing that the teacher uses positive phrases in giving feedbacks	4.04	High
2. Believing that the teacher consistently uses an encouraging method when correcting homework.	3.89	High
3. Observing that the teacher will use positive High emojis.	3.86	High
4. Thinking the teacher will give grades for every High Item in the homework.	3.79	High
5. Noticing that the teacher discusses the High outstanding answer in class.	3.71	High
Category Mean	3.86	High

C. Methods of utilizing corrective feedback

1. Tending to immediately review my homework after it has been corrected.	High	3.88
2. Using search for a method on how to correct my mistakes.	High	3.82
3. Finding myself reviewing my previous homework before completing new assignments.	High	3.79
4. Observing that I try to compare my mistakes on writing homework.	3.71	High
5. Acknowledging that others will help me to correct my mistakes in my homework.	3.61	High
Category Mean	3.76	High
Overall Mean	3.81	High

Corrective feedback content. The corrective feedback content was rated by the participants as High, with a category mean score of 3.86. This means that it is always oftentimes manifested by the students. In addition, Item No. 1 Observing that the teacher uses positive phrases in giving feedbacks which garnered the highest rating with the mean score of 4.04 which described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Moreover, in Item No. 5 Noticing that the teacher discusses the outstanding answers in class got the lowest-rated mean score of 3.71, with a high descriptive equivalent. This means that the level of corrective feedback in terms corrective feedback content is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Methods of utilizing corrective feedback. The methods of utilizing corrective feedback got a category mean score of 3.76, which described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Moreover, in Item No. 1 Tending to immediately review my homework after it has been corrected got the highest mean score of 3.88, which described as high. This means that is oftentimes manifested by the students. Meanwhile, Item No. 5 Acknowledging that others will help me to correct my mistakes in my homework is the lowest-rated item which has a high category mean score of 3.61, which described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Summary on the Level of Corrective Feedback

Presented in the Table 3 was the overall level of Corrective Feedback. Data showed that the highest mean performance expectancy the highest means score of 3.86 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the corrective feedback content is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Table 3. *Summary on the level of Corrective Feedback*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Motivating method	3.81	High
Corrective feedback content	3.86	High
Methods of utilizing corrective feedback	3.76	High
Overall	3.81	High

On the other hand methods of utilizing corrective feedback obtained a mean score of 3.76 which considered to be the indicator got the lowest mean. This implied that corrective feedback in terms of methods of utilizing corrective feedback is oftentimes manifested.

Level of Student Engagement in Filipino

Shown in Table 4 is the level of student engagement, obtained an overall means score of 3.67 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the learning engagement is oftentimes manifested. Student engagement as the dependent variable of the study has three indicators namely: behavioral engagement, cognitive engagement, emotional engagement.

Behavioral Engagement. The behavioral engagement was rated by the participants as high with a category mean score of 3.53. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No. 1 Feeling pleasure when I participate in small group discussions, obtained the highest mean score of 3.72, with descriptive equivalent of high. This means that it is always manifested by the students. However, in Item No.5 Feeling anxious when I come to class every day got the lowest-rated mean score of 3.18, which described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students.

Cognitive Engagement. The cognitive engagement was rated by the participants as high with the category mean score of 3.64 which described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, the item no. 1 working hard on a paper or project that required integrating ideas or information from previous sources got the highest mean score of 3.94 which described as high. To further, item no.5 discussing my grades or assignments with my instructor got the lowest-rated mean score of 3.39 which described as moderate. This means that it is sometimes manifested by the students.

Table 4. *Level of Student Engagement*

Variables and Indicators	Mean	Description
A. Behavioral Engagement		
1. Feeling pleasure when I participate in small group discussions.	3.72	High
2. Feeling more confident when I raise my hand in class	3.69	High
3. Observing that I taking good notes in class, and come to class every day.	3.69	High
4. Asking questions in class or contributed to class discussion.	3.39	Moderate
5. Feeling anxious when I come to class every day	3.18	Moderate
Category Mean	3.53	High
B. Cognitive Engagement		
1. Working hard on a paper or project that required integrating ideas or information from previous sources.	3.94	High
2. Putting together the ideas or concepts from different courses when completing assignments or during class discussion.	3.79	High
3. Looking over class notes to make sure I understand the materials	3.59	High
4. Preparing two or more drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in	3.51	High
5. Discussing my grades or assignments with my instructor.	3.39	Moderate
Category mean	3.64	High
C. Emotional Engagement		
1. Feeling grateful when I work with other students on projects during class.	3.92	High
2. Having a great time in class that encourage me to learn more	3.85	High
3. Really desire to learn the materials to better equip with knowledge	3.82	High
4. Feeling being confident that I can learn and do well in the class	3.77	High
5. Feeling happy when I get tutor or taught by other students paid or voluntary.	3.76	High
Category Mean	3.82	High
Overall Mean	3.67	High

Emotional Engagement. The emotional engagement got the category mean score of 3.82, which described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, item no. 1 feeling grateful when I work with other students on projects during class got the highest mean score of 3.92, which described as high.

This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. On the other hand, item no. 5 feeling happy when I get tutor or taught by other students paid or voluntary got the lowest-rated mean score of 3.76 described as high. This mean that it is oftentimes manifested by the student.

However, behavioral engagement obtained a means score of 3.53 which considered to be the indicator got the lowest mean. This implied that student engagement in terms of behavioral engagement is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Summary on the level of Student Engagement

Table 5. *Summary of the level of Student Engagement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Behavioral Engagement	3.53	High
Cognitive Engagement	3.64	High
Emotional Engagement	3.82	High
Overall	3.67	High

Presented in the Table 5 was the overall level of Student Engagement. Data showed that the highest mean performance expectancy the highest mean of 3.82 with descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that student engagement in terms of emotional engagement is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Correlation Between Corrective Feedback and Student Engagement

The data revealed that the level of corrective feedback of BSED students have a total mean score of 3.81 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the corrective feedback is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. On the other hand, the data also revealed that the level of student engagement of BSED students have a total mean of 3.67 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the student engagement is oftentimes manifested as perceived by the respondents. The results of significant correlation between corrective feedback and student engagement were presented below.

Presented in Table 6 is the result of the significant correlation between corrective feedback and student engagement with an R- value of .490. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected within this context. This impose that there is a positive, moderate and significant relationship between corrective feedback and student engagement.

Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, this means that there is a significant relationship between corrective feedback and student engagement. This further explains the two variables simultaneously increases or decreases together, without giving any data on which on of the variables causes the increases or decreases of either variable.

Table 6. *Significant Relationship Between Corrective Feedback and Student Engagement Among Filipino Major Students*

<i>Variable Correlated</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>R-Value</i>	<i>P-Value</i>	<i>Decision @ =0.05</i>
Corrective Feedback	3.81	.490	<.001	Ho Rejected
Student Engagement	3.67			

The Lived Experiences of Filipino Major Students with Regards to Corrective Feedback and Engagement as a Student

There are three essential themes that emerged from the in-depth interview and focus group discussion of the participants on the first question. Before the presentation of the results from the interviews and discussions, the profiles of the participants for the qualitative data collection are presented in Table 1.2. The table represents the participants' profiles for the qualitative phases selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a 1st year, 2nd year, 3rd year, or 4th-year Filipino major education student in KCAST. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants' sex and year level. Further, Table 3.1 deals with the lived experiences of the Filipino major students in corrective feedback and student engagement. The essential themes that emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for research question number one consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Experiencing Difficulty in Finding Meaning on Feedback. Taking into consideration the information and data gathered as shared by the participants through In-depth Interview and Focus Group Discussion, college students particularly the BSED Filipino students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology expressed varying perspective on their experiences in terms of their learning engagement of corrective feedback. Majority of them shared that they experience difficulty in finding meaning on feedback. There are two code/categories such as personal experiences and complexity in understanding in engaging with corrective feedback, above is the first category being mentioned.

Personal Experiences. This is the first code of the probed on the first probed issue. Students experience difficulty in finding the meaning of the corrective feedback given by teacher that can cause mis interpretation in both teacher and student. They believed that corrective feedback can be a hinder in their ability if the feedback given by the teacher is not clear to understang and having complexity in terms of reasons why it being given employing in each life.

It can cause misinterpretation, lack of improvement, frustration, among students in teaching and learning where unclear feedback acts as a barrier to learning, where the absence of clear communication through preferred language hampers learning engagement.

Similarly, Participants 3 recognized the difficulty of corrective feedback that he/she experienced specifically in grasping the meaning or the intent behind the feedback provided by their instructors which can hinder their ability and it has a huge impact on their engagement having difficulty can give a negative impact and challenges in learning process of the student and it can be also a hinder. She affirmed.

“Kanang challenge nga akong na experiences is having difficulty to grasp the meaning or intent behind the feedback provided by instructors or peers, which can hinder my ability to implement some kay dali ra makasabot but nay puy uban na mag lisod but however I always do my best to understand every meaning.” (IDI-03)

(Challenges that I experienced is having a difficulty to grasp the meaning or intent behind the feedback provided by instructors or peers, which can hinder my ability to implement Some can easily understand but however there are other that having a difficulty but I will do my best to understand every meaning.)

Table 3. *Experiences of Students with Regards to Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Category/Ideas</i>	<i>Essential Theme</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Difficulties in comprehending corrective feedback	<p>Encountering difficulty in comprehending that can cause confusion.</p> <p>Unable to grasp the meaning or intent behind the feedback which can hinder ability to implement effectively.</p> <p>Experiencing difficulty due to unclear statement being delivered</p> <p>Facing hard time in understanding the meaning behind corrective feedback.</p>	Personal Experiences with challenges	Experiencing Difficulty in Finding Meaning on Feedback	Sewell's Cognitive Load Theory
Complex interplay between corrective feedback toward student engagement	<p>Does not have a clear direction on how to improve mistakes.</p> <p>Experiencing unclear way of delivering which give a huge impact on ability</p> <p>Have unclear and not comprehensive feedback may cause confusion.</p> <p>Inconsistency may bring to difficulty to discern a clear path for improvement.</p>			
Effective ways of giving corrective feedback	<p>Positive yet comprehensive feedback clearly and concisely.</p> <p>Employing positive approach that led to positive behaviors and attitudes that greatly impact in their student engagement.</p> <p>Positive environment were teacher and students have a good communication with appropriate manner.</p> <p>Concise point of feedback in a way teacher should pointed out the things need improvement.</p> <p>Straight to the point with good manner.</p> <p>Used as motivation to strive hard more, enhance my ability to provide useful response in future.</p> <p>Part of learning process to be aware on things that need improvement.</p> <p>Learning is a normal process which reflects on behavior, on how to handle things in concise and appropriate manner.</p> <p>Positive impression on corrective feedback by accepting, valuing and putting in mind how corrective feedback improve learning.</p>	Positive feelings in corrective feedback	Motivated feeling in the class with clear and Positive Feedback	Broaden-Build Theory
Diverse perspectives in corrective feedback	<p>Maintaining positive attitudes to improve and viewing feedback as growth and development.</p> <p>Being able to fully understand by seeking clarification to my teacher.</p> <p>Motivation to strive hard always look on brighter side.</p> <p>Straight to the point considering appropriate words delivering feedback</p> <p>Provide a detailed information and pointing out errors in appropriate manner.</p> <p>Provides students specific information on their performance, in a clear and comprehensive way.</p> <p>Considering those appropriate words when she delivers feedback with clear and precise, that can enhance our understanding.</p> <p>Formative that provide in learning process to allow the students to make adjustments and improvements.</p>			

Additionally, Participant 5 recognized having difficulty if does not have a clear direction on how to improve mistakes which can lead to misunderstanding the specific feedback that has a huge impact on learning experience on student. He cannot easily understand the concept, because of that it takes time to process to comprehend each feedback given to him. He said that:

“Uhhh, challenges that I faced sa actively engaging sa corrective feedback is like it kanang having difficulty to comprehend gud sa mga things especially sa unsay ginapasabot sa feedback. I can't easily grasp the main ideas because of unclear statement being deliver

to me that it takes time for me to process para makasabot ko.” (IDI-05)

(In my experience, the challenges that I faced in engaging in corrective feedback is having difficulty to comprehend things, what was the feedback being conveyed. I cannot easily grasp the main ideas because of unclear statement being deliver to me that it takes time for me to process for me to understand.)

Furthermore, participant implies that the students having a hard time in understanding the meaning of the corrective feedback that can have negative impact. On the performance of a student, as well as to overall performance. There are instances that can give confusion on students especially on the areas need to improve and to address. Having unclear giving of feedback resulted to negative consequences. As Participant 7 stated,

Ang mga na experience nako nga challenges is having a hard time to understand the meaning behind corrective feedback and sometimes having a hard time kung unsay ginaingon sa naga feedback sa akoa cause dili clear ang paghatag sa feedback that can lead to misinterpretation. And naa poy scenario that si teacher is may inconsistency sa paghatag sa feedback which is ma confuse ko pag evaluate sa mga areas need nako I address sa akong performance.” (FGD-02)

(The challenges that I experienced is having a hard time to understand the meaning behind corrective feedback and sometimes having a hard time if what is the feedback being said, because of unclear statement the way it deliver that can lead to misinterpretation. There are scenario that teacher is having inconsistency in giving feedback which give me confusion in evaluating to those area I need to address in my performance.)

Complexity in understanding. As participants revealed during the interview that the student is facing complexity in understanding the feedback if it's the feedback is not clear the way the teacher delivers it. The student being challenged on what step he must do in order to for the feedback become meaningful. There are sometimes I doubt on my capabilities if the teacher give many feedback on my performance. As the participant stated that;

“Uhhhhh.. kanang uhhhhh... akong na faced in actively engaging in corrective feedback is dili clear ang pag deliever sa teacher which maka impact sya sa ability nako nga maka understand. Ma challenge gyud ko unsaon para mahimo ug meaningful ang mga changes sa akong performance kay naay sya lacking sa pag hatag ug feedback sa akong teacher. Naga doubt gyud ko sa akong skills especially if naay feedback nga ginacorrect ko and maka cause sya ug discouragement sa akoa.” (FGD-04)

(I faced in actively engaging in corrective feedback having unclear way of delivering by teacher which give a huge impact in my ability to understand. Ma challenge ko on how to become meaningful changes with my performances because there is lacking when it convey to us sometimes I doubted my skills especially if there are feedback that criticize me that may cause discouragement in my self)

Another complexity being mentioned by the participant during the interview it is easy to have unclear feedback it may result to confusion in every students. She also mentioned that she is afraid to seek for clarification due to the fact that she might received judgement from the teacher, having this negative mindset can influence how the think and how they view things.

“Akong na encounter is kanang importante gyud diay kaayo na dapat clear ang feedback kay sa akong na encountered its not easy to have unclear and not comprehensive na feedback kay maka cause gyud ni sya ug confusion sa mind sa students. I did not seek any clarification because mahadlok ko nga maka recieve ug judgement gikan sa akong teacher and na realize nako nga dili diay sya maayo na butang na I consider kay it may hinder communication in giving feeback.” (IDI- 04)

(I encountered is indeed important to have clear feedback, as what I've encountered it is not easy to have unclear and not comprehensive feedback it may cause confusion in every students minds, as a students I did not seek any clarification because I am afraid due to the thinking that I may receive judgement from my teacher and I realized that it is a bad thing to consider it may hinder open communication in giving feedbacks.

Lastly, it was approved by the participant stated during the interview that due to language barriers like having diverse interpretation of the language the complexity of the language being used can led to mis interpretation having language barrier is not easy to deal with. Students have different level of understanding and capability to comprehend things. As participant 9 mentioned, he stated that;

“Kanang ang mga notable struggle nga akong na encountered kay abot language barriers gyud like lahi ang ginapasabot sa teacher then lahi sad sa akoa which led to mis interpretation and mis understanding nga mag arise kay naay different languages like lisod sya sabton sa level nako as a student ang ginagamit sa teacher na mag struggle ko sa paghatag sa teacher sa corrective feedback niya.” (FGD-04).

(The notable struggles that I encountered is about language barriers like different of what teacher being convey, it also different of what I understand which led to mis interpretations or misunderstanding that may arise because of different languages like having difficulty to comprehend the level of the students used by teacher that's the struggles in corrective feedback given by the teacher.)

Positive feelings in corrective feedback. This is the second code for the probed issue. The participants imparted that they can constantly learn and understand effectively when using positive yet comprehensive. They observed that their engagement is very active. By pinpointing the exact areas that need improvement, recipients can better understand what changes are necessary. By employing these strategies, corrective feedback can be a powerful tool for driving growth and fostering continuous improvement.

In connection with that, students encountered positive and effective ways of giving corrective feedback. They positively gained information retention, a deeper comprehension of the concepts being given to them, and having a feeling good environment, where the teacher gradually discussed from complex to simple, it can give a huge impact on the attitudes and behaviors of the students. as well as it can enhance skills as toward learning. In not crowded environment where teacher and student are present. As he mentioned that:

“The most effective ways of giving corrective feedback para sa akosa kay hinay-hinay ug pasabot sa akosa like bisan complex ang case kay I deliver sya in simple but comprehensive style, sometimes kay maglisod kog understand sa mga butang, so mas better sa akosa if hinay-hinayon. I consider sa paghatag sa ug feedback like giving negative then e sunod ang positive with permission sa student kung unsay dapat unahon ug deliver so that student can be aware and mas better gyud if dili kaayo crowded in a way that mas better if kamo lang duha sa teacher para dili kaayo ulaw.” (IDI-03)

(For me the most effective way in giving feedback is gradually explain to me like complex cases it should deliver in a simple yet comprehensive style, sometimes I encountered difficulty in understanding things. So, it is better for me if slowly process will utilize then having alignment to those necessary things that need to consider in giving feedback like giving negative then followed by positive with the permission of students what should properly to deliver so that students be aware and it is better if the place is not crowded where just the two of you tackled the corrective feedback.)

Moreover, students emphasize how effective if teacher utilized positive yet comprehensive feedback using clear and concise manner. This approach helps maintain the recipient's motivation and confidence while preparing them to be receptive to constructive criticism. And it should not dwell on negative but rather than both positive and negative, delivering feedback in a clear and concise manner ensures that the message is easily understood and actionable. Moreover, delivering feedback in a clear and concise manner ensures that the message is easily understood and actionable. As the participants mentioned:

“Para sa akosa the most effective way is to give positive yet comprehensive feedback and si teacher should explain in a clear and concise manner. And it should not dwell on negative feedback so that student can learn and improve ilang mistakes na iyang na commit. And highlighting what student do well in class para ma boost ilang confidence and motivation to tackle sa areas where they need to grow and consider the feelings of the students.” (IDI-02)

(For me the most effective way is to give a positive yet comprehensive feedback and teacher should explain in a clear and concise manner. And it should not dwell on negative but rather both positive and negative feedback, so that student can learn and improve the mistakes she commits. And highlighting what students are do well in class that can boost their confident and motivation to tackle areas where they need to grow and consider the feelings of the students.)

Similarly, some of the students shared their experiences on how teacher utilize positive approach that can led to positive behaviors that can boost students' motivation, perseverance and can greatly impact on students' engagement. Having positive way of giving corrective feedback can give to positive attitudes and can give huge impact on student learning and to overall performances As what participant 7 said,

“Para sa akosa the most effective way of giving corrective feedback that I believe can greatly impact on student engagement kay by using positive approach that can led to positive behaviors and attitude sa students especially na mag strive hard sila sa ilang studies that can greatly impact sa ilang engagement. And positive approach that can boosts students' perseverance to continue with their studies.” (FGD- 02)

(For me, the most effective way of giving corrective feedback that I believe can greatly impact on students' engagement is by using positive approach that can lead to positive behaviors and attitudes in students especially in striving hard in thier studies that can greatly impact in thier student engagement as well. Positive approach that can boost students perseverance to continue with thier studies.)

Lastly, students convey their taught on what are the effective ways of giving feedback that it should be straight to the point with good manner consider the feeling of students, in a way that still it can boost positively their participation. By acknowledging students' efforts and achievements fosters a supportive and encouraging learning environment. When students feel valued and appreciated, they are more likely to be motivated and engaged in their studies. As participant 9 stated:

“Most effective ways of giving corrective feedback that makahatag ug dakong impact is para sa akosa kay straight to the point gyud with kanang dili gud maka hurt sa feelings sa students and mas maboost pa ang ilang participation sa klase nga pamaagi sa paghatag sa feedback, then kanang naga correct si teacher kay nagahatag pud sya ug mga simple words nga dali ra bitaw masabtan nako.” (FGD-04)

(Most effective ways of giving feedback that give a huge impact for me, is straight to the point with good manner that cannot hurt any feeling of students that may boost more in thier participation in class by giving feedback, then if you corrected by teacher they should utilize easy word that is easy to understand.)

Attitudes of students in corrective feedback. Another essential theme down from the responses during in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The participants mentioned that corrective feedback is normal part of learning process and viewing corrective feedback as valuable guidance for improvement and an opportunity for growth. can impact their receptiveness to it and, consequently,

their ability to learn and grow. It's essential for educators to foster a supportive and constructive feedback environment that encourages students to see feedback as a valuable tool for improvement rather than a source of stress or discouragement.

To further, some students shared diverse perspectives about what specific corrective really is. Most of them expressed the same sentiments based on their insights. Corrective feedback can also be a way in using it as motivation to strive hard more and focus on what aspects need to enhance in order to have a useful responses in development. According to participant

“Uhhmm... when I receive corrective feedback, I will used it as my motivation to strive hard more, I should not dwell on negative feedback but rather I will use it as my knowledge base that may enhance my ability to provide useful responses in future. In this way feedback serves as a valuable tool for ongoing development and refinement”. (IDI-02)

(When I receive corrective feedback, I will used it as my motivation to strive hard more, I should not dwell on negative feedback but rather I will use it as my knowledge base, that may enhance my ability to provide useful responses in future. In this way feedback serves as a valuable tool for ongoing development and refinement.)

Moreover, during the interview student shared different perspectives about corrective feedback and how it affects on the improvement especially in learning process, as being mentioned by participant corrective feedback is part of learning things for us to improve because as she/he mentioned that it is crucial. As he/she stated.

“Nagamanage gihapon nako despite nakarecieve kog corrective feedback kasi para sa akona part sya para makalearn ta sa mga thins na kailangan nato buhaton and syempre para ma aware ta na dapat nato sya iimprove kay diri sa kalibutan daghan pata kailangan na mahibal an and the exact example ani kay corrective feedback”. (IDI-03)

(I manage despite I receive corrective feedback because for me it's a part of learning that I can learn to those things need to do and to those things need to avoid and for us to be aware on things that need improvement because in this world there are things we need to learn and the exact example is the corrective feedback.)

Additionally, during the interview participant mentioned that I still manage my engagement because they didn't take it for granted, also he values it and put it mind the goodness of a specific feedback she received in learning process. Having this kind of mindset is very helpful in order have a good learning environment. She also metioned by stay positive because that is the important things we need to value and consider. As participant 4 mentioned it stated that;

“Even nakadawat kog corrective feedback but still na manage gihapon ang akong engagement because dili nako gina take for granted ang mga butang and gina accept ginavalue gihapon nako ang ginabutang nako sa akong mind ang kaayuhan sa corrective feedback. And always stay positive gyud because that is one of the important thing nga always nako ginaconsider.” (IDI-04)

(Even if I receive corrective feedback but still, I manage my engagement because I didn't take for granted all things but I accept, value and put in my mind always the goodness of corrective feedback. And by always stay positive because that is one of the important things that I always consider.)

Employing corrective feedback positively impacts. This is one of the essential themes that emerged from the responses of the participant in-depth interview and focus group discussion with the code of maintaining positive attitudes to improve and viewing feedback as growth and development. As they mentioned, maintain corrective feedback with positive attitudes, make fully effort to understand the feedback being given, use it as motivation to strive hard. Above are their diverse perspective with it come on corrective feedback.

As stated by participant by maintaining positive attitudes it can be resulted to improvement and development, corrective feedback is a valuable tool indeed, it gives a positive implication on us specially in our engagement. Having positive attitudes is indeed important on how we view and consider a lot of things. Can experience on how to be a positive thinker to any feedback given by the teacher is indeed can help. As stated by participant 6; FGD-01

“kanang maintaining positive attitudes to improve and viewing feedback as growth and development.” (FGD-01)

(It's important to maintain positive attitudes to improve and viewing feedback as growth and development.)

Additionally, participants being mentioned that even if he received corrective feedback I always makes an effort to fully understand. Also, he always ask for clarification understand every detail and how to apply to my works and performances when I received corrective feedback. Because by always makes more effort can give a huge impact specifically on learning process. As a result you can easily comprehend were areas need to enhance and value. By allowing my self to this kind of mindset can give me positive development. As stated by participant 9; FGD-04

“Kuan... even pag maka dawat kog corrective feedback but still gina manage gihapon in a way that I make effort na to fully understand by asking clarifications sa akong teacher para makasabot ko unsay pasabot ato niya na pag feedback and gamiton nako na sya nga butang para makasabot ko para naa koy basehan para sa akong performance and sa akong engagement and ginahuna-huna pud nako unsaon nako sya pag-apply sa akong work or performance. When I receive feedback but naka learn gihapon ko.” (FGD-04).

(Even if I received corrective feedback but I still manage my engagement in a way that I make effort to fully understand by seeking

clarification to my teacher for me to understand and for us to have a basis and engagement, I always think on how to apply my works or performances when I receive feedback. When I receive feedback but still, I can also learn.)

Lastly, statement above was supported As stated by participants 10 FGD-05, as she when I receive feedback she used it as motivation to strive hard no matter what feedback she received, she always look on the brighter side and she also mentioned that she always put effort extra effort to improve better. Being positive can led to a happy and motivated life, when I receive a corrective feedback I use it as a tool for opportunities and motivation.

“I still manage my engagement despite I receive corrective feedback from my teacher because I used it as motivation to strive hard no matter what feedback I received but I always look on brighter side and wala pud ko nagapanatag but instead akong mas ginaspagan pa nako kung unsay akong ginabuhay always.” (FGD-05)

(I still manage my engagement despite I received corrective feedback from teacher because I used it as motivation to strive hard no matter what feedback I received but I always look on brighter side, I did not reassurance but instead I always give diligence to whatever I do always.)

Experiencing Improvement in Learning and Engagement due to Constructive Feedback. The last theme that was drawn from the responses of the participants from their in-depth and focus group discussion under the experiences of Filipino students with regards to corrective feedback with the code/category of encouraging mechanism of feedback. The participants mentioned that if students commit mistakes their teacher did not say it straight to the point, were she always consider the feelings and emotions of her learners, and she uses appropriate words when she deliver a feedback with clear and precise, so that students have a guide in learning process. And it has a huge impact on their engagement. As participant 1 stated above;

“Based on my experience, I noticed na if we commit mistakes, kay dii niya gina estorya na straight to the point naga correct sya in a good way like gina consider niya ang appropriate na mga words if naga hatag sya ug feedback with a clear and precise, para mayroong basehan ang mga estudyante in actionable steps that we can enhance our understanding. When she gives her feedback, she consider first in acknowledging our efforts which is good para sa among motivation, it has an impact gyud on our engagement to participate mor sa iyang class. Naa syay mga way na ganahan mi labi na in delivering her lesson.” (IDI-01)

(Based on my experience, I noticed if we commit mistakes, she didn't say it straight to the point she corrected me in a good way like considering those appropriate words when she deliver a feedback with clear and precise, as her students they guide us in actionable steps that we can enhance our understanding. When she gives her feedback, she considers first in acknowledging our efforts which is good in our motivation, it has an impact on our engagement to participate more in her class. She has a way that we like especially in delivering her lesson.)

To further, one of the participants mentioned that provide detailed information with regards to their performances, as well as simply pointing out errors in appropriate manner is one of the good characteristics of a teacher. As well as, they mentioned teacher consider their feelings, give encouragement and give motivation to strive hard on their studies. One of the encouraging mechanisms in which students can increase their engagement. As being stated by participants 2;

“For me, teacher should provide a detailed information regarding to my performances and give feedback beyond simply pointing out errors in appropriate manner like, considering my feelings as a student and most of all teacher should give encouragement so that students can learn more, and give motivation to strive hard in their studies. Pointing out that you doing well in classroom of course it will reinforce positive behaviors and attitudes that can motivate students to continue putting a lot of effort and striving for improvement.” (IDI-02)

(For me, teacher should provide a detailed information regarding to my performances and give feedback beyond simply pointing out errors in appropriate manner like, considering my feelings as a student and most of all teacher should give encouragement so that students can learn more, and give motivation to strive hard in their studies. Pointing out that you doing well in classroom of course it will reinforce positive behaviors and attitudes that can motivate students to continue putting a lot of effort and striving for improvement.)

Moreover, as participants revealed during the interview that most of the students prefer the specific type of feedback that is formative that it allow students to make adjustments and improvements on their performances. For me this is an appropriate tool in order to make good environment were teacher and student that can help understand and develop a huge and useful things.As the participants stated that;

“Para sa akoa is formative feedback kanang mag provide during sa learning process para ma allow ang students to make adjustments and improvements in real-time, na maka help sa amo na makadevelop ug deeper understanding always.” (IDI- 04)

(For me specific type of corrective feedback that give a huge impact on students specifically in classroom setting is formative that provide in learning process to allow the students to make adjustments and improvements in real time that can help in myself to develop deeper understanding always.

Lastly, participant 7 support the statement above, stated during the interview one of the specific types of feedback that give a huge impact in a way it should deliver in general statement. So that student can reflect on their own, as the participants mentioned as well, having this type of feedback they cannot feel ashamed on the mistakes they committed to be criticize by other classmates. As the participants being stated that;

“For me the specific type of corrective feedback that give a huge impact on students especially in classroom setting is kanang e general statement para maka reflect ang students unsay need namo iimprove, naa mi time to think kung unsa ang dapat namo buhaton, general feedback para matago ang privacy sa students inig maka commit sila ug mistakes para dili maolawan or ma criticize sa ubang classmates then ang students na ang bahala na mag identify kung sila ba or dili. And by using positive impression ang dapat gamiton sa teacher, maka reflect, maka learn and at the same time ma boost pa ilang engagement.” (FGD-02)

(For me the specific type of corrective feedback that give a huge impact on students especially in classroom setting it should be in general statement for student to have privacy and to reflect things need improvement, they have time to think what they need to do if we commit mistakes so that students cannot be ashamed of being criticize by their classmates and the role of the students is to identify their mistakes. Teacher should possess using positive impression always to reflect and learn at the same time to boost engagement.)

Insights of Filipino Students with Regards to Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement

Table 4. *The Insights of Filipino Major Students with Regards to Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/Category</i>	<i>Essential Theme</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Importance of dealing corrective feedback that may improve learning	Crucial role to become aware on the necessary things that you need to correct, it can also improve performances. Crucial way for us to learn especially in our performances in improving or in correcting mistakes, we should consider it as valuable tool. Opportunity for learning and growth as means of refilling our skills and becoming better version of ourselves. Open- minded create opportunity to grow, seek clarification is needed in taking actionable step toward improvement. Essential skill for growth and improvement as a student, its crucial to approach it with an open mind to learn. Valuable tool in guidance indeed for improvement as well as opportunity to gain new insights perspectives and skills.	Improve learning and achieve success	Corrective Feedback is Valuable Tool That Give Opportunity to Learn	Expectancy-value theory
Importance of providing feedback instruction and support services	Focus on areas that need improvement rather than dwell in criticism and communicate with the teacher to address ang concerns. Experiencing criticism is meant to help you grow. View it as an opportunity for improvement, seek guidance from teachers on how to address specific areas of concern. Instead of dwelling on negativity encourage to learn better. As future educators we must ready to any criticism throw to us even if it hurt but still continue to strive hard then show them that you can. Embracing mistakes and creating step on how to accept and when you are ready give yourself courage on what are the necessary things need to consider.	Importance of embracing criticism	Turning criticism into motivation for self-improvement.	Growth Mindset Theory
Importance of maintaining growth mindset on corrective feedback as tool valuable	Always value positive mindset Always having a positive mindset, no matter what challenges you faced Maintaining growth mindset is be positive always and view corrective feedback a valuable tool for improvement. Embracing open-minded that will help to recognize the areas for improvement. Embracing challenge and opportunity for learning and setting realistic goals improvement and celebrating programs that achieve along the way. View it as opportunity for improvement and growth. Positive attitude and a willingness to learn, turning into a valuable tool for personal and academic growth. Students can gain valuable insights, identify and make necessary adjustments to enhance their performance. Pointing out your mistakes, having a basis on how you should avoid unnecessary things specially in corrective feedback.	Importance of Positive Attitude to corrective feedback	Foster Positive Mindset and Appreciation for Corrective Feedback in Students’ Engagement that Give Huge Improvement	Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

This table display the scrutinized and synthesized notions in the insights of BSED major in Filipino with regards to their strategies, techniques, and realization in corrective feedback given by their teacher. Their reason and points of advice on sustaining student engagement when receiving corrective feedback were also gathered and analyzed. As a result of the thematic analysis, three (3) essential themes emerged namely: Corrective Feedback is Valuable Tool in Learning Effectively, Turning Criticism into Motivation for Self-improvement and Growth, Foster Positive Mindset and Appreciation for Corrective Feedback Increase Students' Engagement. From these three themes, three (3) significant codes/ categories were yield after probing the participants with related issues. Finally, these themes were supported by various theoretical perspectives such as Theory Expectancy- Value Theory, Growth Mindset Theory, Self Determination Theory (SDT).

Corrective Feedback is Valuable Tool That Give Opportunity to Learn. The first essential themes being emerged corrective feedback is a useful tool because it gives people the chance to own up to their mistakes, encourage a growth mindset, and give specific instructions on how to get better, all of which support ongoing learning and skill development. The participants mentioned that corrective feedback is very crucial because by this we can learn and improve a lot of capabilities in my performances. In order to gain new insights and perspective skills

“Corrective feedback is very crucial because we can learn and improve a lot of capabilities in my performances. And we should listen to those things being corrected because it is for our own good. You should view corrective feedback as valuable tool in guidance indeed for improvement as well as opportunity to gain new insights perspectives and skills.” (IDI-02)

(Corrective feedback is very crucial because we can learn and improve a lot of capabilities in my performances. And we should listen to those things being corrected because it is for our own good. You should view corrective feedback as valuable tool in guidance indeed for improvement as well as opportunity to gain new insights perspectives and skills.)

Moreover, participant revealed during the interview that it mentioned that corrective is a crucial way for us to learn in improving mistakes, that has a huge impact in engagement of the students. Also, the participant mentioned that corrective feedback is indeed a valuable tool. Feedback is crucial for teaching and learning process since it help us to improve our behaviors and performance in a positive development and we can get a understanding on it. We should always consider it as valuable tool to every students and teachers that well surely enhance engagement. As it mentioned that;

“Akong ma share sa fellow students nako inig mag deal kos corrective feedback it is crucial gyud sya na pamaagi for us to learn especially sa atong performances nga mag- improve or ma correct sa mga mistakes, we should consider it as valuable tool.” (IDI-04)

(The things that I can share to my fellow students in dealing with corrective feedback it is crucial way for us to learn especially in our performances in improving or in correcting mistakes, we should consider it as valuable tool.)

To further, another participant mentioned that corrective feedback is important, and it is an opportunity for learning and growth. She/he also concludes that it is means of refilling of our skills as a result we became the best version of ourself. It also important that we should accept and value because it give a huge impact on students. As participant 3 mentioned in statement that;

“In dealing with corrective feedback is important, we should embrace it as an opportunity for learning and growth we can see it as means of refilling our skills and becoming better version of ourselves. We should accept and value it because it can give a huge impact on our self as well as to our studies.” (IDI-03)

(In dealing with corrective feedback is important, we should embrace it as an opportunity for learning and growth we can see it as means of refilling our skills and becoming better version of ourselves. We should accept and value it because it can give a huge impact on our self as well as to our studies).

To further, as elaborated by participant 6 it mentioned that in corrective feedback, we should be open- minded for us to make an opportunity to grow also, it is important to seek for clarification towards improvement. Because in corrective you can learn and improve a lot of things specifically in learning process. Seeking clarification is one of a good thing to do because if there are unclear statement you can easily change it to somethings useful.As the participant mentioned above;

“It is important to be open-minded and you create opportunity to grow, seek clarification is needed in taking actionable step toward improvement.” (FGD- 01)

(It is important to be open- minded and you create opportunity to grow, seek clarification is needed in taking actionable step toward improvement.)

Aside from that, participant 8 made mentioned that corrective feedback is an essential skill for growth and improvement. and when receiving feedback, it's important to approach it with positive attitudes. And it is an opportunity to identify areas for improvement that can enhance your skills. The statement above is participant 8 answer during the interview as she stated;

“For me dealing with corrective feedback is an essential skill for growth and improvement as a student, when receiving feedback its crucial to approach it with an open mind and willingness to learn. Instead of taking feedback personally view it as an opportunity to identify areas for improvement and enhance your skills. When you receive corrective feedback remain calm and composed. Take a

moment to process the feedback before reacting.” (FGD- 03)

(For me dealing with corrective feedback is an essential skill for growth and improvement as a student, when receiving feedback its crucial to approach it with an open mind and willingness to learn. Instead of taking feedback personally view it as an opportunity to identify areas for improvement and enhance your skills. When you receive corrective feedback remain calm and composed. Take a moment to process the feedback before reacting).

Turning Criticism into Motivation for Self- Improvement. One of the essential themes that I take based from the answer of participants in both In-depth and Focus Group Discussion.

Importance of providing feedback instruction and support service. This is the first code, the significance of accepting responsibility for one’s corrective feedback was underscored by participants. This many good attitudes of how it effects on student engagement. It is essential for empowering individuals to effectively give and receive feedback, fostering a culture of continuous improvement, and driving success in personal and professional success. As being shared by participants those students who received negative feedback it is important because he/she used it as a challenge or motivation to grow and improve, she also mentioned that he/she didn’t dwell on negativity because if always think on negative it can cause discouragement that can cause negativity. As he/she mentioned above stated that;

And to those students received negative feedback from their teachers used it as challenge or even motivation to grow and improve do not dwell yourself in negative feedback because it can cause discouragement in yourself, as a result you cannot learn due to negative feedback but instead use it as a motivation to work harder and prove to yourself, those people that you are capable of overcoming negativity.” (IDI-02)

(And to those students received negative feedback from their teachers used it as challenge or even motivation to grow and improve do not dwell yourself in negative feedback because it can cause discouragement in yourself, as a result you cannot learn due to negative feedback but instead use it as a motivation to work harder and prove to yourself, those people that you are capable of overcoming negativity.)

To continue, another participants who made mentioned about the peace of idea with it comes on students who receive negative feedback that you should not deeply put in mind and heart those feedback and show other that you confidently improve from those negative you received. Also, put all effort to learn and improve things, just be positive always. As participant 6 mentioned in her/his statement that;

“As a student my idea with it comes to students who receive negative corrective feedback you should not DIBDIBON those feedback and make it as a way to improve better and show people around you that you are capable, even you faced hard time when you receive, put extra effort on your work with perseverance, determination, always think that you did a great job hence be positive always” (FGD-02)

(As a student my idea with it comes to students who receive negative corrective feedback you should not negatively put in mind those feedback and make it as a way to improve better and show people around you that you are capable, even you faced hard time when you receive, put extra effort on your work with perseverance, determination, always think that you did a great job hence be positive always).

Another mentioned he/she stated in statement to those students who negatively experience feedback, has a mindset that criticism meant to help you grow and develop, it is an opportunity for improvement. The participant made mentioned that receiving feedback is a hurtful process but by this you can be an effective student,it is a natural process for us to learn. Instead of dwelling on negativity encourage yourself to learn better. As participant share her/his idea it stated that,

My ideas to my fellow students who encountered negative feedback that always remember that criticism is meant to help you grow. View it as an opportunity for improvement, seek guidance from teachers on how to address specific areas of concern. Receiving negative feedback from teacher can be challenging experience for students, often leading to feeling of frustration or inadequacy. However, its crucial to recognize that it is an essential part of learning process that you need to accept. Instead of dwelling on negativity encourage yourself to learn better.” (FGD-03)

My ideas to my fellow students who encountered negative feedback that always remember that criticism is meant to help you grow. View it as an opportunity for improvement, seek guidance from teachers on how to address specific areas of concern. Receiving negative feedback from teacher can be challenging experience for students, often leading to feeling of frustration or inadequacy. However, its crucial to recognize that it is an essential part of learning process that you need to accept. Instead of dwelling on negativity encourage yourself to learn better.

Moreover, he highlighted as a future educators she said that she always ready to any criticism because at the end of the day it is part of the process. Even if it hurts but still we should continue to strive hard to reach the desires we have. She/ he also emphasis the in every challenge encountered never give up even you receive bad, continue to pursue it because it has a huge impact on you as a student. As participants mentioned his answer above it stated that;

“My advice to those students who received negative corrective feedback DIBDIBON but instead put it in your mind if what was the teacher said. As future educators we must ready to any criticism throw to us even if it hurt but still continue to strive hard then show

them that you can. And most of all don't give up even if you received negative coming from teacher continue to pursue because they always guide you. They give negative feedback for us to learn from our mistakes and to be aware." (FGD-04)

(My advice to those students who received negative corrective feedback DIBDIBON but instead put it in your mind if what was the teacher said. As future educators we must ready to any criticism throw to us even if it hurt but still continue to strive hard then show them that you can. And most of all don't give up even if you received negative coming from teacher continue to pursue because they always guide you. They give negative feedback for us to learn from our mistakes and to be aware.)

In addition, participants mentioned that when you received negative feedback it is important to set aside all the emotions you feel and reflect on criticism to step improvement and motivation for self- improvement. Also, he/she mentioned that we should embrace our mistakes, it is important in teaching and learning process that was being mentioned by participants 10 above;

"And to those students who received negative feedback from their teacher it is important to set aside all the emotions you feel and reflect on what are constructive steps to improve. It's all about turning criticism into motivation for self-improvement. And embrace your mistakes and create a step on how to accept and when you are ready give yourself courage on what are the necessary things need to consider." (FGD-05)

(And to those students who received negative feedback from their teacher it is important to set aside all the emotions you feel and reflect on what are constructive steps to improve. It's all about turning criticism into motivation for self-improvement. And embrace your mistakes and create a step on how to accept and when you are ready give yourself courage on what are the necessary things need to consider.)

Foster Positive Mindset and Appreciation for Corrective Feedback Increase

Students' Engagement. Third theme under insight they experienced that positive mindset and emotions that give as well a positive attitudes towards students. As Participant 3 one of the strategies being mentioned is having positive mindest and embrace feedback, and she make it as motivation as always. As he stated that;

Para sa akoa is strategies nako is always have positive mindset lang gyud no matter what challenge you faced as long as naay ka sa positive side makaya ra gyud nmo ang tanang ma receive nmo and e embrace nmo ang feedback then make it as your motivation to strive hard kanunay." (IDI-03)

For me, strategies is always having a positive mindset, no matter what challenges you faced as long as you have positive side you can cope to all feedback you received and embrace feedback then make it as your motivation to strive hard always.

To further Participant 5 believed that one of the strategy in maintaining growth mindset is being open-minded that will surely help to recognize areas of improvements. One of the valuable thing in order to absorb new information that can be resulted to develop new skills that will help in learning process. Allow students becoming open-minded they can view feedback as a chance for growth rather than as criticism. As participants being mentioned that;

"In my opinion, the strategies as a student that you should use to maintain growth mindset kay makatabang sa imo to recognize the areas for improvement that you may not have been aware recently and for you to absorb new information that can acquire our skills na magamit nmo sa imong learning process that can be a result sa growth mindset." (IDI-05)

(In my opinion, the strategies as a student that you should use to maintain growth mindset when receiving corrective feedback is having open-minded it will help to recognize the areas for improvement that you may not have been aware recently and for you to absorb new information that can acquire new skills that can help to employ in learning process that can be a result to growth mindset.

As Participant 6 highlighted about strategies for maintaining growth mindset when receiving corrective feedback she mentioned that she view it as challenge and opportunity for learning and setting realistic goals for improvement. Also, she mentioned that she always seeking support from peers and mentors. As participant being stated above;

Strategies for maintaining growth mindset when receiving corrective feedbacks view it as a challenge and opportunity for learning and setting realistic goals improvement and seeking support from peers and mentors and celebrating programs that achieve along the way." (FGD-01)

(Strategies for maintaining growth mindset when receiving corrective feedbacks view it as a challenge and opportunity for learning and setting realistic goals improvement and seeking support from peers and mentors and celebrating programs that achieve along the way.)

Moreover, Participant 10 said that strategies that she used is positivity that increase her motivation and no matter whar challenges she faced its important to be positive that she mentioned that can help to reach her desires and goals in life. Additionally, she mentioned by cultivating positive mindset can help to contribute happy life. As he stated above;

"As what I've said earlier the strategies that student use is always be positive that can increase motivation and productivity no matter challenges you faced being positive can help you to reach desires and goals you want. By cultivating positive mindset, it can contribute

to a happier, fulfilling life specially it can cause to growth mindset.” (FGD-05)

(As what I’ve said earlier the strategies that student use is always be positive that can increase motivation and productivity no matter challenges you faced being positive can help you to reach desires and goals you want. By cultivating positive mindset, it can contribute to a happier, fulfilling life specially it can cause to growth mindset.)

As Participant 1 also mentioned that he should listen carefully to every correction because it will surely help you always. Listening carefully play a crucial role for you to be aware and understand what was being corrected to you. One of the important things I always consider because it has a huge impact to every students performance, were they can identify the areas need to improve. Also, she stated

“Kuan... You should listen carefully to every correction kay para rapud na sa imong kaayohan and for everyone. By approaching corrective feedback, it will give a positive attitude and a willingness to learn, you can turn it into a valuable tool for personal and academic growth.” (IDI-01)

(You should listen carefully to every correction because it is for your own good and for everyone. By approaching corrective feedback, it will give a positive attitude and a willingness to learn, you can turn it into a valuable tool for personal and academic growth.)

As participant 2 share his realization about corrective feedback and the important information especially in his performances that having corrective feedback is a good foundation on how to improve and be aware of the things need to be avoided. He also conclude like what other participant being mentioned always having a positive side in receiving feedback, do not dwell on the positive but it should be balance and he also stated that seeking clarification is an essential role to fully aware what teacher being convey to me. As the participants being mentioned above he say that;

“As a student my realization is corrective feedback is important especially in our performances for us to have a good foundation on how to correct our performances on how to improve and how to avoid the things that we should do and don’t. And always be positive if you received any feedback, always think it as for your own good, then thinking on negative side and it is essential during giving feedback you should seek clarification to become fully aware what teacher being convey. Corrective feedback is indeed important.” (IDI-02)

(As a student my realization is corrective feedback is important especially in our performances for us to have a good foundation on how to correct our performances on how to improve and how to avoid the things that we should do and don’t. And always be positive if you received any feedback, always think it as for your own good, then thinking on negative side and it is essential during giving feedback you should seek clarification to become fully aware what teacher being convey. Corrective feedback is indeed important.

Then other participant, mentioned specially participant 5 she realized about her experiences in corrective feedback is valuable way for growth and development as a student. She also mentioned that mistakes is just part of a process that you need to overcome for not to repeat it again. And you should be thankful to those people serves as a tool in improving by giving guidance and advice. Participant 5 emphasizes how lucky she was surrounded by good people who are willing to help and give encouragement. As participant 5 being mentioned above that;

Akong realization about sa akong experiences kay uhhh... kanang corrective feedback is kanang valuable way for growth and development as a student. And mistakes is just a part of a process that you need to overcome for you not to experienced it again the mistakes you commit to be better and perform better everyday and you should.” (IDI-05)

“My realization upon reflecting my experiences in corrective feedback is a valuable way for growth and development as a student. And mistakes is just a part of a process that you need to overcome for you not to experienced it again the mistakes you commit. they know how to identify areas for improvement as well as they can provide much needed support and encouragement you should be thankful for them.”

In addition, another participants emphasizes her realization about corrective feedback she said that she is not afraid to it but rather embrace it as opportunity for growth and development. She also highlighted that corrective feedback is a reflection of her performance and it is the key in which she can reach those goals and desire she had. She believe that there is a step or process that she always consider, by this she can experiences success in her life. As well as, by corrective feedback she can observe were areas need for improvement and were areas need to decrease, it serves as guide on me, as to contextualize her answer. Corrective feedback is indeed important on everyone it serve a reflection in our abilities as worth as a student, it emphasize how corrective feedback is the key on how reach goals and awareness. As participant stated she mentioned that;

“My realization about corrective feedback is we should not avoid or afraid of it but embrace it as opportunity for growth and improvement. It serves as reflection in your abilities or your worth as a student or what you have show on your performances By corrective feedback we can also see it if were area we belong or suitable, were areas need for improvement, indeed corrective feedback is important as a future educator.” (FGD-04)

(My realization about corrective feedback is we should not avoid or afraid of it but embrace it as opportunity for growth and improvement. It serves as reflection in your abilities or your worth as a student or what you have show on your performances, By corrective feedback we can also see it if were area we belong or suitable, were areas need for improvement.)

Lastly, as participant elaborated that she always listen actively and engage herself to changes that feedback may bring. She also conclude that she always thankful to teacher because by these she became aware on her performances. As she stated above, she mentioned that;

My realization upon reflecting on corrective feedback given by teacher is you should listen actively and engage yourself to changes that feedback may bring, you should be thankful to your teacher because they give feedback for you to be aware on your performances. You should be thankful as well teacher provides guidance on how to correct errors that you can use to improve in the future.” (FGD-05)

(My realization upon reflecting on corrective feedback given by teacher is you should listen actively and engage yourself to changes that feedback may bring, you should be thankful to your teacher because they give feedback for you to be aware on your performances. You should be thankful as well teacher provides guidance on how to correct errors that you can use to improve in the future.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on corrective feedback of teacher and student engagement among Filipino teacher education students in a local college carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The third research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 5 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents the focal points in the first column which contains the aspect or focal points of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in preceding columns.

Table 5. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

<i>Aspect or Focal Points</i>	<i>Quantitative Findings</i>	<i>Qualitative Findings</i>	<i>Nature of Data Integration</i>	<i>Axiological Implications</i>
Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement of Behavioral Engagement	On the table 1.2 on motivating method observing that teacher includes page number of the textbooks so I can review my knowledge which has mean of 3.72 which is rated as high. On the other hand in table 1.2 on the level of student engagement in terms of behavioral item no. 1 feeling pleasure when participating in small group discussions with the mean of 3.72 which is rated as high.	Table 3.1 on the code of attitudes of students in corrective feedback with core ideas, did not take for granted all things, accepting and valuing and put in mind always the goodness of corrective feedback.	Merging-converging	Teacher who always guide students by putting page numbers can increase knowledge and resulted to students who feel pleasure in participating in small discussion, they did not take all things for granted because they value feedback as a valuable tool for improvement.
Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement of Cognitive Engagement	On table 1.1 under the methods of utilizing corrective feedback item no. 1 about tending to immediately review my homework after it has been corrected with the mean of 3.88 which is rated as high. Table 1.2 on the level of student engagement in terms of cognitive item no. 1 working hard on paper or project that required integrating ideas or information from previous sources with the mean of 3.94 which is rated as high.	Table 3.1 on the code of encouraging mechanism of feedback with core ideas of provide a detailed information and pointing out errors in performances in a clear and comprehensive, appropriate manner to grasp huge information that can help to generate ideas.	Merging-converging	Students who used mechanism by providing information in pointing out errors in their performances are tend to immediately review and work hard on paper or projects because they have previous sources were it help in grasping a huge information that can help to get many ideas on how to evaluate easily their performances.
Corrective Feedback of Teacher and Student Engagement of Emotional Engagement	Table 1.1 feeling when working with other students on project learning with mean of 3.92 which is rated as high. Also, on the table 1.1 believing that the teacher consistently uses an encouraging method when correcting homework.	On the table 3.1 with the code of positive feeling in corrective feedback with the core ideas. Employing positive approach that led to positive behaviors and attitudes that greatly impact in their student engagement. And also, having positive environment were teacher and student have a good communication with appropriate manner.	Merging-converging	The high rating for employing positive environment were teacher and student have a good communication approach that may led to positive behaviors and attitudes that have a huge impact on student engagement such as student feel pleasure participating in small discussions.
	As well as on emotional engagement	On table 3.2 the code of	Merging-	Participants acknowledge the

Effectiveness of giving method of corrective feedback that can greatly impact on students' engagement and learning	<p>in table 1.2 acknowledge that other will help me to correct my mistakes in my homework which has a mean of 3.61 which rated as high.</p> <p>On the table 1.1 under the methods observing that the teacher explains how to check mistakes which has mean of 4.02 which is rated as high. On the surface of under corrective feedback content in item 1 observing that the teacher uses positive phrases in giving feedback which it has a mean of 4.04 which being rated as high, item 2 believing that the teacher consistently uses an encouraging method when correcting homework (M= 3.89), observe that teacher will use positive emojis (M= 3.86) which is rated as high.</p> <p>In table 1.2 engagement item 2 about having a great time in class that encourage me to learn more (M=3.85), item 3 I really desire to learn the materials to better equip with knowledge (M= 3.82) which is rated as high, item 5 I feel happy when I get tutor of taught by other students paid or voluntary (M=3.76),</p>	<p>importance of positive attitude to corrective feedback with one core ideas, embracing open-minded that will help to recognize the areas of improvement.</p> <p>On table 3.1 with the code of instructors delivering strategies reinforcing positive behaviors and attitudes that can motivate students to continue putting a lot of effort and striving for improvement.</p> <p>On table 3.1 with the code of positive feelings in corrective feedback about employing positive approach that led to positive behaviors and attitudes that greatly impact in their student engagement.</p>	<p>converging</p> <p>Merging – converging</p> <p>Merging-converging</p>	<p>importance of open-minded attitude in order to recognize the areas needed for improvement by valuing help of others.</p> <p>Participants who feel positive methods given by the teacher can have a huge impacts on their motivation and learning to strive more, give there outstanding performances to every task they need to do.</p> <p>Students who engage with positive approach of corrective feedback can led to encouragement to learn and desire to materials to better equip with knowledge, being happy to be tutored by someone to increase their understanding this can greatly impact their engagement in learning process.</p>
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The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which display the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results.

Corrective Feedback motivating methods of Teacher and Student Engagement of Behavioral Engagement. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on the on motivating methods of teacher rated as observing teacher explains how to check mistakes high. Also, the item, noticing the teacher supports me with resources so I can improve my abilities is rated as high. This result is connected with the qualitative findings, which is themed as accepting, valuing and put in mind the goodness of corrective feedback. It is then safe to say that qualitative data converges quantitative.

Corrective Feedback methods of utilizing Teacher and Student Engagement of Cognitive Engagement. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on methods of corrective feedback rated as high is tending immediately review my homework after it has been corrected, also the item using search for a method on how to correct my mistakes and item on level of student engagement in cognitive is working hard on paper or project that required integrating ideas or information as high, also the item putting together the ideas or concepts from different courses when completing assignments or during class discussions as high. These results are connected to the qualitative findings under providing detailed information in a clear yet comprehensive to grasp information that help students to generate ideas. Hence, the qualitative data somehow converges quantitative aspects.

Corrective Feedback Content of Teacher and Student Engagement of Emotional Engagement. In the quantitative phase, the specific item on observing that the teacher uses positive phrases in giving feedbacks rated as high, also the item believing that teacher consistently uses an encouraging method when correcting homework. Moreover, on the emotional engagement, respondents rated the item, feeling grateful in working with other students on projects during class and having a great time in class that encourage me to learn more, also the item feeling confident that can learn and do well in the class are all rated as high. These results are connected to the qualitative delivering strategies reinforce positive behaviors and attitudes in striving improvement. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges the quantitative one.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

On the result of corrective feedback of teacher on student engagement, according to their shared insights and experiences through in

depth interview and focus group discussion experiencing challenges, with both positive and negative side of corrective feedback from teachers, however as being mentioned those negative will use it as motivation to strive hard, there's a huge impact on student engagement on how they observe based on their performances. As corrective feedback strategies maintaining growth mindset.

To conclude, this highlights the significance of tailored feedback approaches in educational settings. By implementing these strategies, both of teachers and students can enhance learning and support students' development as well as engagement.

Given that the correlation analysis showed that both corrective feedback and student engagement aligned with the study course were highly attributed on teaching and learning process, encouraging them to utilize corrective feedback as a way of being aware of their performances they have, based on the shared insights and experiences of participants. It is recommended that students may approach corrective feedback with an open mind, recognizing that it is intended to help them to improve their engagement. They should remember that receiving corrective feedback is a normal part of learning so that we can enhance our performances and as participants mentioned when you receive negative feedback do not let those emotions dominate but instead use it as inspiration to strive more and improve more.

Moreover, based from the qualitative phase results on the experience of Filipino education students with regards to corrective feedback may acknowledge and normalize the emotions they may experience while facing corrective feedback as self-doubt, pressure and unmotivated as they shared same negative emotions and that is a natural process. Furthermore, those differentiated insights shared may be used to meet and improve future endeavors. Lastly, it is recommended that future researchers may investigate other variables that could fully correlate the relationship between corrective feedback and student engagement.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lysa D. Loayon

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Meugna, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines